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CREATING RECIPROCAL VALUE PROPOSITIONS THE CASE OF THE IMPROVEMENT OF THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF DEMENTIA PATIENTS AND THEIR CAREGIVERS

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ABSTRACT

This study is concerned with the way designer's build-up and maintain shared values and uncover the unmet needs in a network of partners in the context of service innovation. It draws attention to the activities related to the probe and learning process of creating value propositions that are not dichotomous, but reciprocal. We study the case of the improvement of the quality of life of dementia patients and their caregivers. In this research we apply the method to create so-called 'experience flows' for onset dementia patients and related stakeholders, such as caregivers, relatives etc., to uncover unmet needs and opportunities for innovative solutions with lighting. The contribution of this paper lies in the application of design driven tools to create value for multiple stakeholders. One of the major findings of this paper is that the experience flow method enables designers to involve stakeholders in the analysis and synthesis process of design without being fenced by existing problems and scenario's.

Keywords: value proposition, probe and learn process, design management.

INTRODUCTION

There is a growing amount of literature that indicates the potential of designerly approaches to realize societal benefits by designing breakthrough products and services that create new meanings (Verganti, 2008, Brown, 2009). For such innovations the knowledge, experience and insights from multiple parties is needed to create a holistic view on the unmet needs and emerging opportunities (Trimingham, 2008). At the same time, solutions for a higher-level opportunity, such as the improvement of quality of life of dementia patients and their

caregivers, need to be supported by multiple stakeholders to realize the intended benefit (Pol & Ville, 2009). Designers typically have a strong background in understanding users through empathy, and are used to work with seemingly opposing requirements (Martin, 2009). This paper argues that these designer skills can be extended to uncover unmet needs of other stakeholders as well, and to create a solution that addresses shared value for these stakeholders. In this study we refer to a value proposition as the common shared product values and the related system functionality that contribute to all stakeholder values.

Customers perceive value by trying out new products and services, in search of new performances (Carpenter and Nakamoto, 1990, Rindova and Petkova, 2007) and experiences (Pine & Gilmore, 1999). Producers engage value by creating products that deliver more returns on their investments (Moran and Ghoshal, 1999, in Rindova and Petkova, 2007). In traditional perspectives on value creation the process is perceived as single directional (Ballantyne et al., 2010). As such, a value proposition is a deliverable offered to customers and/or users. Yet, the different stakeholders have various perceptions on values (Rindova and Petkova, 2007), often compete with each other for different market segments (Christensen and Rosenboom, 1995), often have different incentives (Casadesus-Masanell and Yoffie, 2007), and often have various challenges for success (Adner and Kapoor, 2010). Thus, to create sustainable value propositions and the related successful designs the value creation process has to be reconsidered.

The value proposition is created in a process of interaction among various stakeholders. The value

proposition becomes based on reciprocal values (Ballantyne et al., 2010). In this context a designer needs to facilitate this process by exemplifying and synchronizing all reciprocal needs in a network of stakeholders in order to create reciprocal value propositions. This value might evolve during the design of new products, but also changes after market release due to new emerging market patterns. The questions addressed in this research project are:

- A. *How can designers efficiently make sustainable value propositions and prototypes that address the reciprocal needs of multiple stakeholders?*
- B. *How can we effectively learn from the emerging patterns in order to uncover new opportunities and unmet needs?*

In this paper we use the case of improvement of the quality of life of dementia patients and their caregivers. The opportunities for designers' to create value with intelligent lighting solutions have increased tremendously in the past decades. Various studies have postulated that light can have a good influence on the sleep-wake cycle, which is one of the common symptoms that lead to institutionalization of dementia patients, as caregivers can no longer cope with patients with distorted sleep-wake rhythms.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND METHOD

The discussion has shown that current environmental circumstances require designers to interact with stakeholders in order to come up with feasible value propositions. It is also noticeable that this interaction requires a proper process of value propositioning to prevent loss of momentum through all kinds of barriers and complexities. This process is

multifaceted, iterative, and requires abilities to communicate early probes, concepts, but also prototypes and final versions. In addition, a thorough analysis is required in order to understand the problem field. The types of innovations we investigate are multifaceted, complex, and require an in-depth understanding. Yet, interviews and meetings with stakeholders might be dominated by current problems in existing circumstances, which might fence the solution space. One of the most important postulation is that the experience flow method supports the process of analyzing the problem space without setting clear the solution space. It is expected that stakeholders are enabled to ideate about solutions. In this study we focus in particular on the interaction, and the role of design in optimizing this activity. The intention is to combine the advantages of an extensive problem analyses without being fenced in the solution space. We intent to stimulate stakeholders in getting engaged in the design activity and, consequently, to be involved in the synthesis phase of design.

This study adopts the probe and learning process proposed by various authors (e.g. Lyn et al., 1996). As such, we are particularly interested in methods to create reciprocal value propositions together with stakeholders. In order to conceptualize the elements of value propositions current research follows the system theoretic aggregation / de-aggregation principles are used to analyze the dementia care process. The subsequent levels are distinguished: (1) Society; (2) Ecosystem; (3) Organization; and (4) User (den Ouden, 2011). The propositions should address the unmet values in each of the levels. The study presented in this paper is part of a larger research project. The overall goal of the project is creating a platform for future design and research

Figure 1. Conceptual framework.

projects, a platform through which others can explore the process and get insight through the collected information.

PROCEDURE

In order to get real insight in how this process and its segments we approach the problem through engaged research (van de Ven, 2007). The methods were implemented in an action research project in an empirical setting. Innovations in healthcare are often initiated in complex network of several parties with each their individual values. The challenge is to analyze and understand the various values of stakeholders in the dementia process (stages, people and symptoms dementia patients have to deal with), and then secondly make it understandable for others. Therefore the study can be classified as a longitudinal field study.

Based on the literature and practical experience from industrial cases, several methods were identified that offer partial solutions. These were combined into a 'probe and learning approach' that consists of three important elements (see Figure 1):

1. *Extracting values and opportunities through experience flows* - Personas of the target group whose needs and values are representative of a typical patient, that help to understand the motivation for sustained use of the new solution, and provide insight in the changing needs and values of time as a patient's condition develops;
2. *Creating stakeholder insight loops through workshops* - gathering of multiple stakeholder insights in fast iterative loops through interviews, workshops and observations, to facilitate the development of value propositions and concepts that are consistent with primary or evolving insights from key stakeholders;
3. *Multidisciplinary opportunity mining and prototyping by investigating value networks* - learning by doing, creating a holistic user experience across all aspects of the product service system, and communication by quickly building and testing prototypes.

These steps are investigated in a real life social innovation design project. The project is started in January 2011, and consequently, we only present preliminary results in this paper.

DATA COLLECTION

Since the process of creating reciprocal value propositions is an iterative process the data collection during this process covers four stages.

First, a process overview is created based upon "cold"-research. Information from the first iteration is based on desk research. Quickly information can be gained about what dementia is and what it means for patients. It is more difficult to find the relationships of parties, how a dementia patient and his/her relatives are positioned in this process, or what the differences are between dementia's patients. Thus, *secondly*, observations were made to get insight in patients, clinics and other professional environments were held. Observations gave in depth insights in the possible scenarios and the value network. A group of dementia patients and relatives are visited in mental health care institutions. It was found that individuals working with dementia's stakeholders operate mainly in their own domain. The *third* iteration of the experience flow extraction process was based on interviews with professionals from the field, each working with dementia patients. Expert interviews giving insight in the detailed steps patients go through and how different scenarios can turn out. During these interviews also personal problems (thus opportunities for design) arise in the operating of the system. Important insight from the expert interviews and observations was that various expert may hinder new interventions because of their resistance to new ideas and approaches. Interesting might be to investigate how social innovations could be convincing through meeting their values. The *fourth* step was the creation of the value network. This value network was created iteratively during a workshop with several stakeholders from the dementia process. During the workshop we motivated the stakeholders to actively and mutually create a value network. To guide the stakeholders, and still keep focus on the patient and family, over personal values. The process was initiated by discussing the values of the patient and the family. Then we gradually extended the network overview, and eventually added the stakeholders themselves to the network.

CASE STUDY RESULTS

THE SOCIETAL PROBLEM

Due to an increase of elderly people as a percentage of the population in the coming decades, our society is confronted with more and more people suffering from dementia and dementia. This leads to an enormous pressure on patients, but also on caregivers. Especially the informal caregivers that are directly connected to the dementia patient are seriously burdened by their beloved ones. 98% of the informal caregivers have problems with care process leading to physical and emotional problems such as overtiredness, insomnia, and depressions (Brabants Actieprogramma Dementie, 2011). The investigated project aims to develop solutions to improve the quality of life of dementia patients and their caregivers. Among the most important other stakeholders of the dementia case are also various industrial governmental organizations that could benefit from the improvement of the situation of the dementia patient and their caregivers. The case study aims to investigate the process of creating reciprocal value propositions in a stakeholder network of both governmental funded organizations and private owned firms.

DEMENTIA & LIGHT CASE

Elderly patients with dementia are next to cognitive decline confronted with disturbances of mood, behavior, and activities of daily living (Lee, et al.,

2003; Purandare et al., 2001; González-Salvador et al., 2000). Circadian rhythm disturbances have been associated with these symptoms (Riemersma-van de Lek et al., 2008). Indeed, light has a modest benefit in improving some cognitive and non-cognitive symptoms of dementia (Riemersma-van de Lek et al., 2008). Previous studies with light therapy with institutionalized patients with dementia have shown that the effects of light therapy are slowly increasing; nevertheless they have significant effect on the mood of the patients, and their sleep/wake cycle (Riemersma-van de Lek et al., 2008). This delivers opportunities for the improvement of the quality of life of onset dementia patients and their caregivers. Due to lack treatment possibilities for dementia, various approaches could be developed for the symptom management to reduce the need of institutionalization. Especially the effects of lighting therapy on the sleep-wake cycle, offer opportunities, as this is one of the common symptoms that lead to institutionalization of dementia patients (Wagenaar, 2010).

Various studies on the effects of light therapy on the on dementia are available (e.g Van Someren et al. 1999; Weldemichael & Grossberg, 2010; Riemersma-van de Lek et al., 2008). Also in various researchers are active in the development of lighting solutions in industrialized environments (e.g. Hoof et al., 2009). Given the fact that many clinical applications and approaches to the prevention of dementia symptoms

Interactive Flowchart : DEMENTIA

Explore the process a dementing person goes through

Figure 2. Experience flow

exist there is a growing need to develop interventions that are embedded in real life settings. In order to have a societal impact it is intended to develop solutions that reduce the overall workload of the dementia disease on home caregivers both formal and informal. To develop successful interventions the values of various stakeholders need to be addressed, such as therapists, nurses, but also partners and family.

EXPERIENCE FLOW

Through our hands-on approach we ended up with an interactive experience flow, a platform that integrates:

1. user perspectives, all stakeholders and their interaction with the system are investigated,
2. expert views, all experts are enabled to include their perspectives,
3. process logic, the sequences and reciprocity of experiences and activities are represented.

Figure 2 illustrates the experience flow of the dementia process. The possible routes people experience when diagnosed dementia are diverse. The colored lines give examples of three possible persona’s that are connected to the dementia case:

- **Persona 1: Perfect scenario.** An ideal patient flowing through the process as the stakeholders and professional care givers would prefer it.
- **Persona 2: Doom scenario.** A story of a person who seems to be rebellious in the system and is a worst case scenario for the process and its stakeholders.
- **Persona 3: Individual scenario.** A personas somebody going through the dementia Process on his/her own and all the service/trouble this ads.

These personas represent three possible and general scenarios through our proposed system. At each stage its point of view and feeling is explained. In this way the stakeholder is able to analyze the process together with the experience patients have.

Based on the cash flow presented in Figure 3 a more in depth value analysis is done of the stakeholders

involved. Based on our preliminary analysis several stakeholders could be invited in a workshop. In the workshop the most important values were iteratively extracted and analyzed.

Through the analysis of the dementia process the most important parties involved became present. As we were able to get into depth information of these stakeholders we could identify their needs and values from our information. In the analysis, the focus was not only on the cash flow, but also the flow of other values. Figure 3 describes the most important monetary flows among the stakeholders. Figure 4 gives an overview of the value flow model that resulted from the case study (see Approach for the procedure).

Figure 3. Cash flow.

Figure 4. Value flow model

PRELIMINARY FINDINGS

Anchored on the findings of the iterative study several problems and design challenges are extracted. Table 1 shows the critical incidents during the dementia process. Table 2 gives an overview of opportunities.

Various incidents are extracted based on the experience flow, while others are based on the discussions during the workshop. In the process of creating, using and adjusting the experience flow several critical observations were made.

First of all, it was found that during the process of searching opportunities individual stakeholders have complexities in understanding overall process and therefore might lose the overview and their position in the process. As a consequence, when following a single user or stakeholder in the dementia process to find opportunities, might lead to local optimizations. For this reason various personas and perspectives are integrated into the experience flow.

Second, an interesting finding was that the participants were able to make their findings explicit by creating a value model. During the workshop we build with the participants iteratively a value network. These values were divided in personal values and value streams. The workshop was divided in two groups. Both groups developed a different version of the value model. Furthermore people were able to communicate and discussing their perceptions. However, sometimes the people are a bit restricted by the chose value model constructs. During this workshop most of the intervention opportunities were found by looking at the (dis-) balances in the value model.

Third, it was observed that based on the experience flow method people where able to not only think about the problems, but also contribute to solution development. When asked people were able to pinpoint improvement possibilities in the experience flow.

DISCUSSIONS

Based on this study, several recommendations are made for advancing the process of interaction with

stakeholders to come up with feasible value propositions. The findings suggest several tentative guidelines concerning the ‘probe and learning’ process of value propositioning. In this paper we develop a method, so called ‘Experience flow method’. It is anchored on the assumption that in order to be able to create new meaning in complex social innovation projects an in depth multi-stakeholder analysis is required. Yet, one of the key dangers of analyzing the current situation is an over focus on existing problems and circumstances. One of the key findings is that the method enabled stakeholders more easily to iterate between problems, opportunities and solutions. This complements to the growing literature on design of intelligent systems and services in the context of complex societal challenges.

Our objective was to investigate the process of creating reciprocal value propositions. The experience flow, as currently constructed enabled both to create shared values and iterate between problems and solutions. The experience flow method makes the contribution of design more clear and it empowers stakeholders to be involved in the design activity. The creativity and idea generation are stimulated in a group setting. It helps designers to extract shared problems, to find shared opportunities, and develop intelligent systems that create shared values. This study can be seen as a first attempt. As part of the larger project we will try to investigate new mechanisms to create reciprocal value propositions in complex societal problems and based on that create intelligent systems and related services. Furthermore, we will search more in-depth for new patterns our data.

Conclusions

CONCLUSIONS

In this research we analyze the dynamics of value creation in a design process from a multiple stakeholder perspective. We postulate the ‘experience flow method’ to extract the most important shared values and design opportunities. In order to design intelligent lighting systems that create value for all the stakeholders, the designer should establish a value proposition. As such, the value proposition comprises the shared values among

the stakeholders (e.g., increase health for patients, lower costs for insurance companies, higher profits producers) and the related intelligent lighting functionality (effect on the circadian rhythm, persuasive technology) required for the development of an intelligent lighting solution. The case study has illustrated that the experience flow method helps to create insight in the unmet needs of the various stakeholders, and supports the process of understanding the shared values. The case study also gave practical insights in how the individual and shared values can be visually represented, and how this can be used in the creation of value propositions for intelligent solutions that require the support of multiple stakeholders.

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Table 1. Critical incidents during the dementia process

Phase	Description critical incident
<p>Realization In this phase individuals become aware of what dementia means and how to recognize signs and symptoms that could be related to dementia.</p>	<p><i>Many stakeholders involved</i> -Several organizations (e.g. GP, dementia Nederland, government) are actively trying to inform people about what dementia is and what its symptoms are and what complications are connected to this disease. These organizations try to do this to familiarize people with the symptoms and experiences of persons suffering from dementia.</p> <p><i>Difficult to diagnose</i> -When the disease begins to develop at a patient certain symptoms of the disease will occur. It needs to be said that with every patient the symptoms can be totally different. Sometime the symptoms are clear and can be easily identified and sometimes the symptoms are much more subtle and difficult to detect. In addition, the reaction of the patient and close relatives can also differ a lot from patient to patient. The reaction people have depends heavily on what knowledge they already have about the disease and what their attitude towards the disease is. When the symptoms begin to occur time will pass before they are taken seriously. This will mostly depend on how severe the symptoms are and how the attitude of the patient and relatives are. People that recognize the symptoms can go to their GP but it is also very common people go professionals for other reasons, falling over or headaches for example which are actually caused by dementia's disease. The arrow going directly to the nursing home represents the situation in which an individual is being internalized due to aging. A patient developing dementia in this stage is a common scenario.</p>
<p>Diagnosis The second phase in the process is called "Diagnosis." And the title already reveals pretty much what this section is about. In this phase an individual will come in touch with professionals, either their GP or other specialized people.</p>	<p>In this phase the patient knows something is wrong and acts upon the signals and symptoms to discover what is going on. In this phase it will become clear if the patient is really suffering from dementia. Mostly people will go to their GP for the initial symptoms or problems and explain what is wrong. When the GP suspects it could be dementia he/she will send the patient to a specialized clinic.</p> <p>Occasionally people have other signals like motor skill problems which could be caused by dementia. In this case they first go to other clinics or departments before going to the specialized memory clinic.</p> <p>From this stage some arrows are leaving the flowchart. These represent the people that actually have something different than dementia that are causing the problems. These will have to go to other clinic specialized for that specific case.</p>
<p>Arrange An individual enters this phase called "arrange" when officially diagnosed with a form of dementia. A patient together with either family and/or professionals, will make a plan for how to move on from this point.</p>	<p>A patient can be in very different states of dementia influencing the specific plan they will make for the future. Sometimes a patient is still able to live at home for a couple of years, and sometimes the dementia has already developed to such a point that they will have to be taken into a nursing home almost immediately.</p> <p>Because the world of professional care can be very complex and people have a lot of possibilities for getting the care specified for their needs, a case-manger will be assigned to the patient. The job of these case-managers is to have knowledge about all the possibilities and guide people to the best care for their situation.</p> <p>Further on a patient can make choices for the next phases. For example how is he going to adapt his or her home situation according to the development of dementia? Which care would he desire when the partner of family takes over the care. Or in what way would a patient like to be treated after care at home is not possible anymore. Not to forget, some people might not make plans because they still do not accept the diagnose.</p> <p>For the patient this phase is the hardest psychologically as the acceptance of a diagnosis is a very difficult process and the realization that a person is going to be dementing further in the next months to years is very hard to deal with. For a partner/family this phase is also hard but all they can do at this point is to make sure there is a plan and provide support where needed.</p> <p>At this point the patient has to be officially diagnosed by the CIZ as a dementing person to be registered as such at the government for financial coverage of extensive and specialized care. More information on this can be found in the costs layer.</p>

<p><i>Informal care</i> The situation described in the “informal care” phase only applies when the patient has a family or has friends to take over the care. If a patient is alone in this process the patient will be able to live at home for a much shorter time. With the use of home-care routine tasks can be taken over and the time can be prolonged.</p>	<p>Informal care is the phase where the patient is beginning to rely more and more on relatives and/or close friends to take care of them. This can range from minor to major dependence. Often the caring family or friends choose how far they go in this care, and how much they can or want to handle.</p> <p>This stage is psychologically most heavy for the family and/or friends as the patient is dementing and the personality of the patient changes. Often this starts with losing the short-term memory and develops to a point of not remembering long-term memory. At some point the patient will need to go to an institute. Nursing homes are for people who need full time care and can handle much less responsibilities. These patients will not need this much care for their situation. Most probably these patients will be send to an elderly home. In this place the patient has a lot more freedom and will only be helped with the tasks he or she really needs help with.</p>
<p><i>Crisis</i> The “crisis” phase is not a common phase in the process, but is an occasional phase that handles crisis situations that can occur when behavioral problems of the demented patient get out of hand. This can happen as early as the arrange phase at home as well as in the nursing home.</p>	<p>When an incident happens specialized institutions can be contacted by the professionals, the partner or the family and will act upon the incident. The GGzE is an institute that has experts who will visit the patient and assess the situation. They will try to change the situation by adapting the care plan and sometimes change medication for the patient. Often when an incident happens at home a patient will have to stay at an internal location at the institute for about 8 weeks or so until his situation is balanced again. Most of the times hospitals have special departments for such internalizations (PAAS) but the GGzE has also a few beds to accomodate people for a while. Often an incident is an indication the patient is in a far step of dementia and from such crisis care they will often go to the nursing home.</p>
<p><i>Palliative phase</i> The “palliative” phase represents the final step in the dementia process; an effort to a qualitative guidance towards the hereafter. Don’t misinterpret the dimension of time represented in this flowchart as 50% of the patients time can be spend in this phase and sometimes even more.</p>	<p>A specialized institute were patients are treated with complex psychiatric and/or organic issues, with more care required, is GGzE “de grote Beek”. Patients here live in different environments specific set for their symptoms and /or behavioral problems. In such an institute three parties define the care plan, these are the responsible doctor (GP, psychiatrist or other) the nurses and the activity managers. They try to offer a balanced plan specific for every individual to maintain quality of life.</p> <p>This phase takes place mainly in the nursing home when people are able to live in such community. For dementing patients there are special departments called PG were people with similar needs live together and share activities and living room. There are two types of PG departments, one is stimulating and one is protecting. As the terms might indicate one is to support interaction and provide stimulus. The other is protecting oriented which tries to provide a routine with minimal social interaction.</p> <p>In the section about crisis it is mentioned that there are specialized institutes who can provide special care if needed. If mild incidents occur the nursing home is able to manage it by their selves and patients might go to a department called PG+.</p>

Table 2. Examples of reciprocal value propositions

Proposition	Description	Source	Stakeholder
Dementia in society	We see an opportunity in how much common knowledge there is in society about dementia and dementia. Mostly it is seen as a memory problem, that's it. It seems that on dementia and dementia rests a certain taboo like used to be on personal well-being previously. We think this is because a person changes from dementia or dementia and he or she cannot be cured from this.	At the dementia-cafe we spotted little knowledge about the disease. dementia Nederland uses their website and ordinary leaflets to spread the message; this is based on pull information while there is very little push information.	dementia-Nederland, non-profit organization to support alzheimer patients and create awareness about the disease.
Awareness and education	For people it is quiet hard to get information about dementia, it isn't clear which symptoms are for what, and how to act accordingly. we think individual institutes try to communicate what they offer, with a different goal ten providing the best support for people. We think the information available at for example a GP should be easier to retrieve, as sometimes too much effort is needed to know what to do. Next we heard stories about GPs who didn't want to listen to patients who knew they had memory issues.	Experience from the dementia cafe were trouble with GPs was spotted. Next to that we spotted people who didn't want to put sufficient effort in getting information and care.	GP, better understanding of dementia and the symptoms
Patient and family relation	This is an opportunity we spotted in the arrange and informal care phase of the process. We saw and heard that dementing people change over the course of the disease both in behavior and character. A person with dementia changes in role from somebody of the same level to share and discuss things with, to a person who you have to care for. What you give is no longer what you gain, this is a very heavy mental and psychological load. Also how long can a partner keep a dementing person at home, and how long is it good for him or her?	Serge Roufs, expert view on patient family relations. User impression at the dementia-cafe.	Family, support in accepting the disease and understanding what is best for self and siblings.
Adoption to care	Several experts we interviewed to investigate opportunities mentioned people usually don't adapt easily to care. In early stages of the disease this is no major problem, but when they have to go to a nursing home or other institute permanently they tend to be resistant and cause problems. What currently works best is bringing people who are diagnosed as early as possible on a regular base inside the institutes to let them become used to it. This is a practical solution and we think there is room for other innovations or at least investigation.	Jan Otten, crisis caretaker expert view. Serge Roufs, general elderly psychologist and manager perspective.	Patient, the one going through the process and causing trouble. Institute, be involved with patient at an earlier stage. Case manager or responsible doctor, knowing of the issue and possible solutions.
Keep People at home	One of the more obvious opportunities, but not less important is the possibility to keep people longer at home. As patients are more cheap for society when they stay at home longer compared to staying internally in an institute. Also in the different institutes, especially in a nursing home the budgets are being reduced and money is scarce. Domotica is a direction which could solve this issue but isn't guided properly at the moment. It seems like domotica is more focused to solve problems like somebody falls often, lets install fall sensors. If domotica would be more opportunity oriented new changes could arise we believe.	Nursing home visit insight.	Patient, being able to manage living on its own better to reduce family pressure/professional pressure. Family, being better at coping with a patient. Nursing home, support innovations in domotica as waiting times will be reduced.
Return of value	When patients are institutionalized they often only cost money without returning anything anymore to society. This opportunity is more focused on a far future, but the idea that in some way these patients can still contribute to society is interesting. Patients in an institute still produce energy and maintain their body, maybe can they do more.	The costs institutionalization asks from society	Patient, in an institute. institute, return value to society through patients.
Nursing efficiency	Nurses often spend a lot of time on basic care of people like cleaning and washing etc. They are being asked to also make contact, because they are closest to the patient who needs this contact. Because the pressure is rising due to budget issues, often this contact moment is skipped while is really important. The opportunity we see is how the nursing processes can become more efficient so the quality can rise.	Nursing in an institute.	Patient, receive better care and more quality in life. Nurses, work better and more efficient.
Social technology	In the future technology will get a more important role, and we also envision this in the dementia process. As we could already see developments in domotica, we think this could also be an opportunity in the nursing homes. Basic routine tasks conducted by nurses, were patients get value from could be taken over by technology. For example rubbing a patient who is already very far in the dementing process doesn't necessarily has to be done by nurses who can provide in more humane tasks.	Technology developmental trends.	Patient, seamless integration of technology in his or her life. Nurse, more time for quality interaction with patients.